

ENRICH in Africa (EiA)

Work Package 6: “Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Plan”

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Work Package Leader: EBN

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Executive summary	The following strategy guides the creation and implementation of the framework conditions for mobilizing stakeholders and disseminating and communicating the EiA Project and Centre activities and the outcomes achieved under the project. It includes clear indicators and all the planned promotional actions to be developed for project activities, especially in the context of the EiA Centre and EiA Champions actions in each country, being implemented throughout the life span of the project, with a special emphasis on mobilising stakeholders, raising awareness, and creating a sustainable market positioning for the EiA Centre.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EiA	ENRICH in Africa
D&C	Dissemination and communication
DCOP	Dissemination, Communication & Outreach Plan
I&A	Incubators and accelerators
URG	Under-represented group

Executive Summary

This document presents the ENRICH in Africa (EiA) **Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Plan (DCOP)**, laying out the strategy that will guide the consortium's communication, awareness raising and dissemination efforts that will be carried out during the project's life cycle.

The document provides an overview of the overall communication and awareness raising process but also the management and monitoring of dissemination and communication activities with a view to ensure the highest possible outreach of the project's activities and results to the relevant key stakeholders. Furthermore, this document describes future steps to be taken in cooperation with other work packages thereby seeking synergies among activities.

In more detail, this document includes the following elements:

- The dissemination and communication **objectives** of the EiA project
- The main **targeted audiences**
- The **dissemination and communication tools and channels** which will be used by the consortium partners aiming to achieve maximum visibility and public awareness (i.e., promotional material, social media, website, newsletters, events organised by the project, external events which partners will participate in, scientific and non – scientific publications, synergies with other similar projects and initiatives)
- The **reporting templates** of the communication and dissemination activities, which need to be completed by partners throughout the project (e.g., activities reporting, templates for participation in external events / conferences, and the overall communication and dissemination reporting template)
- The **key performance indicators (KPIs)** for **monitoring and evaluation** of the dissemination and communication activities implemented under Work Package (WP) 6
- The **roles and responsibilities** of the partners with respect to the project's communication and dissemination activities
- A detailed **timeline** delving into the different stages of dissemination and stakeholder's engagement activities.

It is to be noted that all partners are expected to actively participate and contribute to the implementation of the dissemination and communication activities and according to the dissemination and communication strategy, while the European Business and Innovation Centre Network (EBN) as a leader of WP6, will closely monitor the actions described in the document and provide all the necessary support.

1. Introduction

The aim of this document is to set the operational framework for EIA project and EIA Centre's dissemination strategy towards an effective dissemination of the project's results and to define the frame of reference for EIA partners for an effective dissemination, promotion and communication of the project's activities and results. It is to be noted that EIA's DCOP document is not static in nature. Indeed, the EIA DCOP is a dynamic guiding document that will progress and evolve in tandem with the evolution of the EIA project.

The EIA Communication and Dissemination Strategy is a lively guiding document that will evolve together with the evolution of the project itself: a document steering all activities from the very beginning of the project which will evolve during the whole phase of its execution.

This first edition will be updated when entering the second phase of the project cycle (M13) to properly and timely address the project objectives, according to the evolution of the activities and the actors involved.

All Communication and Dissemination activities in EIA follow the standards and guidelines for dissemination and exploitation in Horizon 2020 projects.

2. About the ENRICH in Africa (EiA) Project

Recent years have revealed an increased focus and interest with regards to the innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems across Africa. Such focus has covered the academic, political, and of course business environment, looking to enhance cultural, technological, and economic advantages. To best explore and engage with this environment, the European Union (EU) through the European Commission (EC), the African Union (AU) and individual European and African organisations have been active in designing several initiatives to best explore the current situation and investment requirements needed to capitalise on opportunities that exist, both for the benefit of African and European countries.

This work has generated scientific cooperation topics that are now active within Horizon 2020 calls, aiming to further support the development of EU – Africa intercultural and research exchange for the mutual benefit of both continents. The outcome has been to develop initiatives and projects that can build on this political momentum and drive the engagement of the innovation community.

With this background in mind, the EIA project comes into play by engaging and working in partnership with a wide variety of successful players in both the EU and African community.

3. EIA Communication & Dissemination approach, objectives, and target groups

The main aim of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy is to **ensure strong outreach and mobilisation and to ensure all non-confidential results reach the proper audiences and stakeholders**, making the most out of them and delivering a benefit for European society.

The D&C Strategy (focussing the WP6 activities) is developed in close collaboration with the Digital Backbone action (focussing on WP7 activities) and the EiA Centre Legacy exploitation Strategy (WP5) to outline and guide the implementation of those measures designed to increase the outreach and sustainable, long term impact of the project at the European and national level of the selected countries in Africa at the same time.

For the whole duration of the project, a strong collaboration between the communication, dissemination and mobilisation and other Work Package leaders is envisaged to harmonise activities and save resources.

Table 1: EiA D&C Descriptions

<p>Communication:</p> <p>To present project activities and general key messages to concerned stakeholders and the public at large, through physical and virtual means.</p>
<p>Dissemination:</p> <p>To specifically disseminate project results to concerned stakeholders, , in order to allow for their exploitation and in accordance with regulations in the field of EC data protection, IPR and commercialisation rights.</p>

During the first year of the project, partners will be mainly focussing on the D&C about the EiA project implementation and goals and reaching out to mobilise the relevant actors who can contribute to making the foreseen EiA Centre Legacy and the intercontinental EU-Africa innovation community a successful instrument for the sustainable creation of an independently operating EiA Centre.

During the second and third year of the project, partners will focus on the D&C as well as exploitation of the consolidated outcomes (virtual training academy, workshops, incubation service portfolio, policy recommendations, etc.) in support of the EU-Africa innovation ecosystem.

3.1 Communication and dissemination objectives and approach

D&C activities will be implemented under WP6 together with the engagement and mobilisation of stakeholders across the European and African innovation ecosystem.

The EiA D&C approach aims to develop a series of actions to promote the project to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner. Research and monitoring will be conducted in order to identify the best strategies for targeting marketing campaigns to the different stakeholder groups, target audience discussed in point 3.2.1. This is achieved using a variety of tools and activities that allow the tailoring of the means used and the messaging to the different stakeholder groups. The strategy fully exploits media convergences and makes use of state-of-the-art social media tools, to allow the project to reach a broad audience.

The communication activities specifically complement the dissemination activities, which are aimed at an expert audience, by ‘translating’ the sometimes-complex results into easy-to-understand media resources that can reach the wider society. EiA aims to foster synergies and enhance communication activities via the online presence of all consortium partners, who already have strong online networks. A set of communication campaigns will be launched per key moments of the project to further boost the visibility of EiA.

3.1.1 Communication and dissemination objectives

EiA’s DCOP goals are:

- a) To develop a strong communication, dissemination, and outreach strategy as the key for successfully engaging with relevant local actors from Europe and target countries in Africa.
- b) To ensure brand awareness and connection to EiA as an organisation and its activities, establishing EiA as a core organisation within the EU Africa innovation ecosystem.
- c) To bring together the triple helix of business, academia, and policy developers in both African and European countries to support the understanding of the requirements for innovation facilitation through core events and community activities.

Under these three overarching goals, partners have detailed main objectives for communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results:

Table 2: D&C Objectives

Communication Objectives	Dissemination objectives	Exploitation objectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform about and promote the project and its benefits to the public at large by highlighting solutions in it contained that tackle societal challenges - Effectively <u>communicate and ensure optimal visibility of results and achievements</u> of EiA and of their key benefits to the EiA Centre - Reach out and activate potential audiences - Increase <u>public visibility and raise awareness around EiA Centre’s service portfolio</u> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe and ensure results available for potentially interested key audiences - Engage with <u>key stakeholder in community building</u> - Enable the transfer of knowledge to audiences that may take an interest and use the results especially in Europe and African target countries - Create the conditions for and support in the effective <u>mobilisation and engagement of potential new EiA Champions</u> applicants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a <u>strong and sustainable EiA Centre marketing strategy and brand</u>. - Identify and implement potential new streams of activity that can enhance the offer of EiA - Establish the <u>EiA Centre as a core organisation</u> within the EU Africa innovation ecosystem - Increase the <u>impact of relevant innovation ecosystem-building enabling policy conclusions</u> derived from the EiA Centre’s outcomes - <u>Define follow-up</u>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Ensure mobilisation</u> via EIA different dissemination channels - Create the conditions for and support in the effective <u>mobilisation and engagement of potential new EIA Champions</u> applicants (business development) 	<p>(business development)</p>	<p><u>activities</u> to be built upon EIA project results (e.g., monitor the EIA Centre’s impact and follow-up activities after project completion)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To <u>establish a collaborative basis</u> for new innovative actions between the EU and its international partners
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3.1.2 Communication and dissemination approach

The EIA D&C approach aims to develop a series of actions to promote the project to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner. This is achieved using a variety of tools and activities to develop targeted messages tailored to the different stakeholder groups.

The EIA D&C approach includes the following:

- a) Clear definition of EIA branding and visual identity
- b) Coherent description of the selected communication channels and tool
- c) Dedicated and tailored outreach strategy for the different target groups
- d) Detailed database mapping of relevant external events, stakeholder platforms that EIA can exploit to further communicate its activities and results
- e) Plan for the dissemination of results in relevant publications and through webinars
- f) Overview of EIA events and activities to promote community building/clustering
- g) Procedures for monitoring the impact of the D&C strategy, using KPIs.
- h) Development of a DCO toolbox, where all partners involved in EIA can access and store visuals, contents, and databases to better perform the various activities just mentioned.

To meet the objectives above, EIA dissemination activities are designed for two different levels:

1. **EiA Project level** – related to internal communication among consortium partners, and external dissemination and communication of EIA project as whole. Focus is set on actors with central roles in or connections to the European and African incubation ecosystem and industry.
2. **EiA Centre level** – related to the awareness raising, stakeholder mobilisation, and exploitation goals towards the calls for EIA Champions and different EIA Centre activities and services. Focus is set on actors with strong affiliation to the business support environment in the selected African countries and in Europe, and on incubators and accelerators in particular. Also, on this dissemination level, EIA partners involved in the stakeholder

interaction/engagement and in the local dissemination within Africa will be cooperating closely and under the guidance of the dissemination leaders.

The EiA DCOP takes both these aspects into consideration. It introduces objectives, tools and activities associated with the communication and dissemination of the EiA Centre along with the mobilisation of stakeholders across the innovation ecosystem of Europe and Africa with the objective to attract clients and raise awareness around the EiA Centre and its portfolio of activities.

The project will, therefore, interact with the target groups in an INFORM and ENGAGE manner.

Once any type of output, result or formal deliverable is ready to disseminate, partners will inform individuals and institutions concerned in various ways and through different online and offline channels (=INFORM).

Moreover, to ensure key-stakeholders are involved during the whole project duration, EiA follows an impact-oriented dissemination strategy that is based on the organisation of a set of different online and face-to-face/hybrid events addressing African and European audiences. This principle ensures that the solutions developed for the business support sector in the target countries are appropriate and meet the specific needs of the locally embedded beneficiaries (=ENGAGE).

3.2 Communication and dissemination target audiences

The engagement of all stakeholders (please see section below for a detailed list of EiA's target audiences) is the key to success for EiA's overall mission. The D&C strategy is therefore addressing stakeholder engagement with primary importance and engagement activities have been organised as a continuous process with implications for each of EiA's work packages (and, particularly WP3 with Capacity Building and Networking for Business Support Organisations, with emphasis on Incubators and Accelerators (BOND), WP7 with the Digital Backbone providing the EiA Community Hub (MET), and WP5 ultimately aiming to build the EiA Centre Legacy and exploiting project results (S2i).

For the activities carried out in WP7 (and WP3), stakeholder engagement plays an even more specific role. To create fertile soil for any future sustainability of the project after its end, successfully connecting stakeholders to the EiA Centre and engaging them in our activities is essential.

Additionally, it is important to underline that the set of activities in the framework of WP6 are designed in a way that ensures optimal visibility of the EiA results. Indeed, the dissemination approach on the one hand focuses on activities that transfer knowledge and results through webinars and publications, and on the other hand community building is a key element. The focus is to bring the innovation community together, to allow the exchange of lessons learned and use synergies between similar projects and initiatives. Focusing on the European - African relationship, the dissemination activities will foster knowledge exchange within the innovation community and connect researchers and entrepreneurs across both continents.

EiA has therefore identified the following core customer groups for its marketing activities (D&C and business development).

3.2.1 The EiA target audiences

Considering the service portfolio that the EiA Centre is set to implement, a diversified set of three core customer segments sub - divided across the European Union and Africa have been identified.

The table below depicts the key actors at whom the EiA Centre's services will be targeted:

Table 3: EiA target audiences

1.a - incubators and accelerators (I&As) - EiA champions in EU (1.A) and in Africa (1.B)

Mainstream incubators and accelerators (I&A) can be excellent intermediaries in support of a strong and connected innovation ecosystem. They are able to understand and respond to the specific needs of entrepreneurs/would-be entrepreneurs on both continents.

To that scope EiA brings together twenty key I&A partners that will function as the first EiA Champions and offer incubation, acceleration, and internationalisation services 'powered by EiA' for entrepreneurs in Africa and Europe, and beyond.

As a first step, EiA is targeting the incubation actors that are part of the project networks (EU|BICs, Impact Hubs, Startup Bootcamp, Co-Creation Hub, I-Hub, and Tech Accelerator's incubation, acceleration, and soft-landing programmes). The project will then open-up its activities and results to other I&As in the EU and Africa to increase the network and number of Champions. To reach out to these organisations, partners will capitalise the connections available within their networks and will support the business development activities of the EiA Centre in its start-up phase. In addition, EiA will capitalise on the good working relationship established with the Africa - Europe Innovation Partnership (AEIP) project thereby seeking to integrate AEIP's members hubs into the EiA Champions programme.

2.Facilitators - e.g., policy makers, academics, corporates, investors in the EU (2.A) and in Africa, focused on sub - Saharan Africa (2.B)

It is a desire of EiA that these stakeholders include representation from across the full triple helix of business, academia and governance, ensuring that the strategic direction of EiA can remain within a constructive framework that can draw down maximum potential benefit to the incubators/accelerators and ultimately the innovative entrepreneurs across the regional ecosystems.

In EiA I&As are at the crossroad of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, EiA will involve in its activities other key stakeholders to promote and stimulate the creation of a strong EU-Africa innovation ecosystem, so that the work done with incubators is integrated in the wider picture and other actors can better understand how I&As can leverage existing networks, resources, and policies, and contribute to shape new ones.

EiA strategic partners within the ENRICH Network, the External Expert Advisory Board, Associated Partners and Strategic Stakeholders will be engaged to provide support across the broad stakeholder chain in EiA's D&C activities. Furthermore, it is important to underline that EiA's Advisory Board brings together representatives from various sectors which include the following:

- Corporate sector (finance)
- Public Body / Authority

- Investors
- Non - Governmental Organisation

3. Entrepreneurs, SMEs, and start-ups in the EU (3.A) and in Africa, focused on sub - Saharan Africa (3.B)

EiA's ultimate purpose is to create a community, enhance innovation capacity, and raise visibility of entrepreneurs to leverage further local market support through the creation of a sustainable business network, the EiA Centre (working to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals), that connects the existing and future innovation networks across EU and Africa.

Entrepreneurs (in the EU and Africa) are essential beneficiaries of the EiA Centre activities, which will ultimately benefit from the various programmes and capacity development of the I&As. EiA highlights female entrepreneurship within the innovation environment by providing a women's entrepreneurial support programme.

4. Media/ multipliers and European society (additional identified stakeholders only for D&C activities)

Media groups will be engaged to provide a wider coverage of the project's intermediate outcomes and the overall EiA initiative. In addition, they may be useful in further communicating the results of the project.

- At regional/national level partners will engage regional media groups to reach out to regional communities and stakeholders and invite them to participate in the experiments (at different stages).
- At European/global level we will be targeting relevant sectoral platforms and media channels. We will further leverage the interconnection with other ENRICH Centres, similar EU-projects and the EiA Expert Advisory Board and Associated Partners members' networks. This will be done through coordinated campaigns for key moments in the EiA project, with the dissemination of press releases, calls (for participation, for tender, calls to action), and events on social media, websites, and mail marketing, for example.

On a practical note, EiA partners will use the dissemination channels of the networks and platforms where they participate, while at the same time EiA will establish contacts and joint actions with other EU-funded projects and EC institutions to disseminate project results.

A database of representative organisations of each of these target groups will be developed to leverage on the consortium's internal network regarding each category.

This database - included in the Dissemination & Communication Toolkit (see below) - will be revised throughout the project's lifetime and will respect the European standards on privacy and personal data protection. It will allow partners to organise the distribution of work, by understanding where contacts are already established and available, and where they need to be built, apart from the key affiliate EU and African projects which will be featured on the EiA website.

4. EiA dissemination and communication tools

EiA communication activities feed the project’s dissemination and mobilisation strategies as of M2. The following section outlines the channels and tools chosen by the consortium to implement these strategies.

When defining channels and tools, partners considered three dissemination dimensions:

Table 4: EiA dissemination dimensions

<p>Online dissemination</p> <p>A set of online tools and channels enabling a two-way communication between the consortium and EiA target groups.</p>
<p>Offline dissemination</p> <p>A set of printable communication and promotion related materials (e.g., leaflets, factsheets, etc.) developed for the project as a whole and for presenting the results achieved.</p> <p>The content of these physical materials may be adjusted and adapted taking into consideration the different context of each network. These materials will be also downloadable from the website and will maximize the results of the project’s activities to be made accessible to the public.</p>
<p>Online and face-to-face events</p> <p>A set of interactive sessions run throughout the whole project lifetime to directly engage with our target audiences, both at local/national and European level. Webinar, training, and workshop series will support the active engagement of EiA stakeholders and a more effective dissemination of the project outcomes.</p>

Partners will be constantly communicating about the overall EiA initiative to the wide European and African audiences and all relevant project stakeholders through online tools, printable materials, and face-to-face events to keep them informed about project activities, opportunities, and results.

These tools and channels have been chosen and designed to convey key messages to EiA stakeholders and are made available to project partners to disseminate the findings and outcomes on a regular basis and involve all stakeholders, from policy makers could/would-be entrepreneurs as final beneficiaries of the actions.

4.1 EiA corporate identity, logo, and visual identity

4.1.1 Corporate identity mix

The EiA corporate identity is the tangible manifestation of the personality of the project. It is the identity that reflects the reality of EiA’s personality and activities. Image and identity are here described by reference to the project’s values, such as diversity, quality, inclusion, flexibility, and community. Surrounded by the three elements behaviour, communication and symbolism, personality element of the corporate identity mix stands at the core.

EiA Personality

To describe the personality - the way the EiA project acts - the mission, achievements in the past, general objectives, culture, and structure components are summarised below.

EiA Mission: to further support the development of EU-Africa intercultural, innovation, and knowledge exchange to the mutual benefit of both regions. The EiA project develops initiatives and programmes that can build on the existing incubation and acceleration networks in both continents and reinforces the engagement of the innovation community.

More specifically, EiA aims to connect European and African incubation and acceleration communities to enhance innovation and co-creation opportunities, reduce and overcome barriers to internationalisation of innovative SMEs and start-ups in Europe and Africa by empowering entrepreneurship and business success.

ENRICH achievements in the past: The European Network of Research and Innovation Centres and Hubs (ENRICH) reinforces Europe as a global leader in research and innovation. Three European ENRICH networks have been set up to date, in Brazil, China, and the USA. The network provides standardised and tailor-made internationalisation support services to European stakeholders (researchers, universities, start-ups, SMEs, etc.) that are aiming to expand and collaborate with organisations in Brazil, China, and the US.

EiA general objectives: The EiA project recognises a dual structure, including ‘project’ and ‘centre’ objectives. At its core, the project pursues the overarching aim to create a sustainable business network, coordinated through a central office that strengthens entrepreneurship and the innovation ecosystem in order to increase productivity and generate employment across Europe and Africa.

The general PROJECT objective is to build the framework, set up the main infrastructure and pilot a business model, which will trial a set of support services and set the foundations towards the establishment of the EiA Centre; an office coordinating a membership-based network of incubator and accelerator hubs across the EU and Africa, called Champions.

The general ENRICH in Africa CENTRE objective is to consolidate the piloted model and activities of the project, thereby becoming a sustainable and valuable organisation within the EU-Africa innovation landscape, complementing, and boosting the services and activities of relevant actors/customers rather than generating a competing model.

EiA culture: Uniquely entrepreneurial-minded, EiA will establish a business centre head office which will draw out, bring together and boost activities and services currently provided by the innovation ecosystem in Europe and Africa, thereby helping to overcome the current fragmentation of information and services, all oriented towards delivering enhanced value and sustainable benefit to the community as a whole.

Following the entrepreneurial culture, the EiA project and centre activities for the EiA foremostly target some of the “main epicentres” of economic growth on the African continent: South Africa, Nigeria, Kenya, and Tanzania. This being said, it is worth noting that through the Champions who are part of the project from the start, EiA will be represented in many more African countries, namely: Senegal, Cameroon, Djibouti, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Madagascar and many other countries.

EiA structure: the EiA project recognises and differentiates between the core project and EiA Centre activities, each operating with their organisational structure in their specific stakeholder environments.

The EiA project consortium consists of key organisations in the innovation field who are also future customers of EiA. The framework will likewise entail a clear governance structure regulating the

relationships and decision-making processes between the project consortium and EiA Centre. Through utilising its project partners as experienced service providers and future customer base, the EiA consortium have developed a bottom-up approach which can promptly deliver services and react to challenges with value-driven solutions (see Figure 1: EiA Consortium Strengths).

The EiA Centre engages and works in partnership with a wide range of the existing successful actors and activities in the EU-Africa community. It focuses on three core segments in the EU and in Africa as a basis of EiA customers: 1-Incubators/Accelerators (EU & Africa), 2- facilitators of innovation activities (EU & Africa) and 3-Innovators/SMEs/entrepreneurs (EU & Africa). The operating reality of the EiA Centre is described in below figure (see Figure 2: EiA Stakeholder Groups).

Figure 2: EiA Consortium Strengths

Figure 1: EiA Stakeholder Groups

Behaviour

Behaviour is the most important and effective corporate identity tool. It is this behaviour on which the project is primarily judged. Elements describing the EiA Project and Centre behaviour include:

Strategy: To generate innovation, a strong and sustainable ecosystem needs to exist. To empower innovation, five core conditions need to be present: diversity, proximity, flexibility, community, and youth (Sergi, G., Nottingham University, 2017). The concept for EiA, and the methodology employed, are therefore based in these core conditions.

Within the grant lifetime (first three years), the EiA Centre will remain an activity of the project, however, it will be branded and positioned separately from an early stage, with its future status being considered within legacy discussions. It is not foreseen that the centre will be acting as a separate legal entity until the end of the grant period. The project activities and its underlying corporate identity follow and support the aim of the project to create a sustainable, independently operating EiA Centre.

The UN's SDGs and the African Union Agenda 2063 goals stand at the core of the EiA concept. With regards to gender balance, the following goals have been considered:

- SDG 5- Gender equality; achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.

- AU goal 17- Full Gender Equality in All Spheres of Life; priority area of: Women and Girls Empowerment

Specifically, EiA aims to highlight female entrepreneurship within the innovation environment, in particular by providing a women's entrepreneurial support programme, such as the EiA Women's Open Innovation Challenge. Generally, EiA will adopt this SDG into all operational and developmental activities.

Products and services: The EiA project delivers a full set of services (Bootcamp training, virtual academy, staff exchange & EU-Africa twinning programme, mentoring programme, advisory services, entrepreneurial support programme, annual congresses, Champions Gatherings, and learning expeditions) to innovators under the foreseen label '*powered by EiA*'. The services are offered on the multi-side EiA platform website which has an integrated Community Hub (provided by EuroQuity) and Open Innovation Challenges section (provided by Agorize) for visitors and EiA members.

The EiA Centre customers will be able, as so-called *EiA 'Champions'* and Associates members (registrants of the digital backbone), to access the high-quality support services, infrastructure, and local guidance and knowledge. Moreover, through EiA Champions network different soft-landing, including co-working space and acceleration programmes - under the model '*powered by EiA*' - will be provided directly to European and African innovators.

Core values: *innovation, entrepreneurship, diversity, quality, inclusion, flexibility, sustainability, co-creation and community* stand at the core of each of the activities and services provided in the EiA project and EiA Centre, during the project duration time span.

Symbolism

Symbolism, also referred to as the visual identity as the most visible component of the EiA corporate identity mix, is described in terms of: Programme title, logo, colour palette, corporate typeface (font), iconography, imagery (photography, illustration, video), language, and layout. The visual identity components are described in the following chapters.

4.1.2 Visual identity

A common visual entity is being created for both the EiA project and EiA Centre, composed by a logo, a set of templates and commonly used documents where same fonts, colours and designs are included.

For this work, EiA consortium relies on the expert graphic design by SPI who develops the logo in "dialogue" with the project partners.

EiA Project logo & symbol

Figure 4: EiA Project Logo

Figure 3: EiA Project Symbol

EiA Centre logo (under construction)

To be confirmed and will be delivered in next iteration of DCOP

EiA Champions seal (under construction)

To be confirmed and will be delivered in next iteration of DCOP

EU funding disclaimer

Being funded by the European Commission, every time partners promote/communicate about the EiA project, **MUST** include the project logo and the EU-emblem together with the following disclaimer:

Figure 5: EU Funding Disclaimer

The EU flag can be downloaded under the following link in different formats and colours (blue and yellow; blue and white; black and white): https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en. All graphic rules regarding the EU flag are available here: <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>.

This information will be made available to project partners in a dedicated document: "EiA Communication Guidelines".

All dissemination materials to be developed and used in the project will be based in this project branding.

4.1.3 Mood board: logo use, colour palette, corporate typeface

To be confirmed and will be delivered in next iteration of DCOP

4.2 EiA offline tools

4.2.1 Project brochure and flyers

Project brochure

A project brochure will be developed to showcase the overall project activities and goals. The brochure will be designed by SPI with inputs from EBN and it will put forward an overview of the EiA consortium partners, showcase the aims of the project and provide the project contact details. The text will be written in English, with essential information on specific activities presented in additional languages, when needed. This will be available both as a printable document and as a PDF document, which can be downloaded from the project website. All partners are invited to print and distribute copies of the leaflet amongst their networks.

Project flyers

Three project flyers will be developed by EiA for the purpose of showcasing the overall project aims, activities and consortium partners. These will be adapted considering the various specificities of the different target regions. The flyers will be provided in an editable file format (e.g., InDesign package), enabling partners to adjust original text sections with translated text in a local language, depending on the context. Additionally, EiA will develop a template to enable all partners to develop project flyers for the purpose of promoting specific activities and opportunities both at territorial, European and African level. This template will be in line with the EiA visual identity and it will include the project logo, the EC disclaimer and EU flag, in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

4.2.2 PowerPoint presentation and report templates

PowerPoint Presentation

A template PowerPoint Presentation will be produced, and a standard presentation will be developed to help partners and stakeholders communicate and disseminate the EiA project during events, workshops, and other activities.

Report template

A report template will be designed and produced by EiA to be used by all consortium partners towards highlighting the project's milestones.

4.2.3 Project poster and roll-up

Project poster

A project poster will be designed to showcase the main information about the EiA Project. This will be available in English and made available to partners in an editable, digital file format (e.g. Illustrator file, InDesign package). The aim of the poster is to inform audiences and generate interest into the EiA project.

Project Roll-up

Two roll-ups will be designed to showcase the main information about the EiA project, which will address the scope, main activities, consortium partners and which will include the EC disclaimer and EU flag. The roll-ups will be provided in an editable file format (e.g., InDesign package), so that partners can replace the original text from English into a local different language, depending on the context.

4.2.4 Infographics and publications

Infographics

A series of infographics will be produced related to the impact and results of the EiA Centre, using data visualization tools to showcase the Centre's benefit and impact on the cross-continental innovation ecosystem.

Publications

A template for publications will be designed by SPI, with the input of EBN, following the agreed EiA colour scheme and visual identity. This template will then be used for all public reports and publications that will be produced under the umbrella of the EiA Centre. This is so that we maintain a cohesive look and feel throughout all the project's outputs.

4.3 EiA online tools and digital presence

4.3.1 EiA project website and community portal

The **EiA Project page** (Task 6.2 – lead: EBN, contributor S2I and MET) is currently under construction and will offer EiA great visibility. The project page will provide a detailed overview of the project, including a description of the challenges we seek to address, EiA's objectives, implementing partners and of course, we will make sure to embed EiA's social media channels. The page will also contain a list of events and news items relevant for the project.

In tandem, the **EiA's Centre website** (Task 7.1 – lead: MET, contributor S2I, IMPH, BOND, AGO, BPI) which is part of the digital backbone of the project and functions as the central hub, is also under construction. The project page and the EiA Centre Website will coexist as two separate websites. The first providing information from a EU project's perspective and the latter serving as a representation of the sustainable business (the EiA Centre), we aim to create.

By M15 the EiA Centre website and its services will be fully functional and will be updated on a weekly basis according to the Centre's planned activities. It will be designed to allow EiA clients (start-ups, SMEs, and corporates), Associate Partners, Champions, and consortium partners to

seamlessly engage through a member only entry function in a user-friendly online experience, but also offer public information on EiA's service offers.

The EiA Centre website are currently envisaged to feature, at minimum, the following sections:

- Main Landing page: this section will be the main landing site containing all EiA information related to content such as service portfolio, costs involved in becoming an associate partner, overview of upcoming events. Also, the main page will feature other sections of the website to redirect users according to their needs.
- Events page: this space will allow the EiA Centre to showcase information regarding upcoming events. Users will be able to see the different events, enquire and purchase tickets.
- Data Hub: this will be a repository that consolidates data reports from various activities and Champions of the project, making them available to the public either free of charge or at a cost. Any reports generated by and sold on behalf of the Champions, will work to a joint revenue share between EiA and the particular Champion, thus providing mutual economic benefit to both parties.
- Funding Advice page: this section will display the different streams of funding available.
- Members only section: this section will be provided for the consortium partners, Champions and registered users (from the other identified stakeholder groups) to communicate with each other, share knowledge, support exchange of valuable data and drive collaboration activities for entrepreneurs in their networks. Within this portal, the following sections will be available:
 - Marketplace - Online stakeholder forum: this section will function as a partnering hub where clients can engage, offer services, request services. Should they wish to find partners or investors that can be beneficial for their expansion plans, they will be able to access the community pages through a separate link to the EuroQuity platform (please see section 4.3.2 for a detailed introduction regarding EuroQuity).
 - Bootcamp, virtual academy and mentorship programmes for Champions: these sections will each provide access only for the Champions to those services provided as a part of the membership benefits. These services will initially be provided to EiA to the pilot Champions, expanding to include qualified Champions who can then provide to their peers once they have finished the training, offering another future revenue opportunity for our Champions.
 - Incubation, acceleration, and soft-landing page: this section will function as the space where incubators, accelerators and soft-landing programmes will be advertised EiA/Champions as a resource for the entrepreneurs. There will be promotional information on the programmes as well as the opportunity for users to engage directly with the service provider.
 - Open Innovation Challenges page: this section will be provided through the Agorize platform and display the different innovation challenges EiA plans to organise and will feature information such as how to get involved, how to apply, how to pose a challenge. Our users will have the choice to either apply for a challenge or apply to pose a challenge.
 - Community Hub page: this section will be available to all stakeholders engaging in the innovation dialogue in EU and Africa, with a specific focus on entrepreneurs and investors and will be delivered through the EuroQuity platform.

- CRM: a customer relationship management tool will be applied in the background of the platform to provide administration and account management support for EiA in engaging and retaining the specific users. It is therefore the place where client data is documented and managed (adhering at all times to GDPR requirements). Also, this section will feature reporting tools and click analytics.
- CMS: the content management system will allow general and section admins to manage their content on the website, from informational to marketing ads. It will be the place where all administrators' tasks will be handled.

Both the project and centre websites will be built and managed following GDPR requirements on data treatment and management. The content displayed online will be written in English aiming to use a relevant and accessible language style as much as possible, making it usable to a wide range of stakeholders.

To monitor website activity, (e.g. amount of traffic, origin of user, demography indicators of users, and on-website behaviour) the website will be monitored through Google Analytics. The indicators collected will also inform of any changes needed to achieve goals. To augment website activity and optimize search engine results, a list of keywords will be researched when creating content. The research results will be verified regularly on a tool like UberSuggest, and its implementations' results will be verified in traffic changes measured on Google analytics.

4.3.2 EUROQUITY platform

The EuroQuity platform will function as EiA's main networking platform in which EiA stakeholders may find relevant partners (i.e., investors). The platform will complement the core aspects of the full website proposition. The set-up of this individual platform will include the creation of the EiA community, including branding and necessary access for consortium members to review and design. The platform will be available in English.

4.3.3 Social Media Accounts (SMAs)

EiA will also deploy its D&C Strategy through **social media**, which will help project partners to amplify their dissemination activities. The SMAs are valuable tools for dissemination and outreach and will act as one of the main avenues to promote the project and its ongoing activities. More specifically, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube channels will be launched in M1, aiming to build an online community of supporters and followers that will then be taken over by EiA once the Centre is established following the completion of the project.

The social media tools selected will be used as a way of complimenting the website and enabling stakeholders to interact with the EiA consortium partners and to engage in the project activities. As such they will serve a double purpose - disseminating information and collecting feedback on stakeholders' experiences with the EiA services and activities.

The social media programme should therefore operate in conjunction with and refer to the EiA Project and Centre websites, to generate website traffic. This content pushed on social media can differ in style but will always need to contain relevant articles and information. The following table provides an overview of the different target groups that the SMAs will address.

Table 5: Social Media Strategy

Social Network	Target Audience	Objective
Twitter @ENRICHinAfrica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EIA Champions ● Entrepreneurs, SMEs, and start-ups ● EU-level funding mechanisms ● Policy makers and implementers ● European & African incubators ● NGOs ● Academic community ● Other Stakeholders 	To enable the effective monitoring of developments and progress in other related projects and relevant organisations; to draw attention towards the EIA Centre and showcase its activities; to identify opportunities for creating synergies with other similar initiatives
Facebook		To draw attention towards the EIA Centre and showcase its activities as well as to connect with similar networks and organisations.
LinkedIn		To have a more institutional approach to boost professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest and possibly involve large corporations, more start-ups, innovation intermediaries and support networks into discussion on the African and European innovation ecosystems.
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EIA Champions ● Entrepreneurs, SMEs and start-ups ● Innovation intermediaries ● NGOs ● Other Stakeholders 	To contribute to increasing the visibility of the project and showcase the EIA Centre activities.

S2i was responsible for the set-up of EIA social media accounts. All partners are expected to contribute, overseen by EBN as WP Lead, by:

- Becoming a follower (follow the page/profile)
- Promoting the accounts in their networks (share/distribute)
- Suggesting relevant profiles for EIA to connect with and follow
- Promoting posts and news through their own organisations' social media accounts.

Twitter @ENRICHinAfrica

A Twitter account will be launched (M1) to act as a platform for building a community of actors interested in cross-continental cooperation between Europe and Africa on innovation and business. Twitter is useful to gain visibility for events and activities within a short amount of time, as the use of hashtag creates multiplier effects that can disseminate a message in a wide and timely manner. As such, the EIA Twitter account will act as a:

- General dissemination and 'heads up' device distributing links that will direct users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., web-portal, newsletter, service platform) and communicating information on project's progress (upcoming events, participation to external events, project results, etc.)
- Newsfeed platform collecting and distributing news from other relevant projects and organisations.
- Feedback platform, a fast and easy contact point through which partners can receive queries and feedback from people.

To monitor Twitter's account performance, the metrics and insights provided by Twitter analytics and Hootsuite will be used.

The following is non-exhaustive list of tags that can be used for EIA posts:

- #ENRICHInAfrica (in line with the other ENRICH projects)
- #EiAIInnovationChallenge, #EiA BusinessChallenge, #EiADigitalChallenge
- #EiAWorkshops, #EiAWebinars, #EiACongress2021,
- #H2020, #BusinessInnovation,
- #EUAfrica

Facebook

Partners will also open and manage a Facebook page due to the popularity of the app amongst African stakeholders. The Facebook page will be used as a means of connecting like-minded individuals and enabling the project to gain visibility amongst stakeholders in Africa. Facebook is extremely useful in getting visibility for events and organising calls to action. It also has a messaging feature built-in, which will be useful in creating a channel for direct communication with those interested in the EIA, where partners will be able to answer questions directly via the chat function. As such, the Facebook page will act as a:

- General dissemination and 'heads up' device distributing links that will direct users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., web-portal, newsletter, service platform) and communicating information on project's progress (upcoming events, participation to external events, project results, etc.).
- Events organising & information distribution (e.g, events marketing, events registration, events live-stream).
- Feedback platform, a fast and easy contact point through which partners can receive queries and feedback from people.

To monitor the Facebook page performance, the metrics and insights provided by Facebook will be used together with additional data and analytics sourced through Hootsuite.

YouTube

The EIA YouTube channel (M1-3) will be created to gather all future videos produced in a single and easily accessible location. The aim of the channel is not only to have a simple video archive but also to enhance the build-up of a strong online community. Thanks to the connection with other similar channels and the integration with the website platform we can use YouTube to further utilise its video capabilities to effectively promote the project's activities.

Project partners are expected to contribute towards the production of the videos and to identify other relevant videos with a view to build up playlists in EIA channel and sharing them with their contacts to maximise dissemination.

LinkedIn

EiA will also make use of a LinkedIn page to increase the project's visibility within a more professional and institutional setting, which allows for knowledge and experience exchange among professionals in the LinkedIn community. The LinkedIn page will be used as a place to showcase the project and its objectives, but also to group all EIA partners under a single professional page where discussions and

news/updates will be hosted. As such, the LinkedIn page will be more project-focused, hosting content that is either directly related to the project (project's latest news, progress, upcoming events, etc.) or involving wider developments that are expected to have a direct impact on the project (e.g., important reports, changes in legislative frameworks, etc.).

Finally, EiA partners should try to involve followers and third parties to initiate professional and expert discussion on issues of common interest. The account will be taken over by the EiA Centre following the completion of the project.

4.3.4 E-newsletter and press release

E-newsletters

EiA produces two types of newsletter, one for public communications and one for the purpose of internal communication. Throughout the course of the project there will be a total of 36 e-newsletters disseminated, out of which 12 will be public communications newsletter and 24 internal dissemination newsletters.

EiA will produce a dedicated newsletter called "Africa Innovation Insights" every 2 months, led by SPI with the support of BOND, AGO and IMPH. These newsletters will summarise the project's progress and inform followers on the project's key-activities, milestones and news from Europe and Africa on key areas such as innovation, technology, business, policy frameworks. EiA will disseminate the newsletters to a wide list of stakeholders interested in the European and African innovation ecosystems. All 18 public communication newsletters will be uploaded on the project's website in a PDF format and distributed via social media channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn).

EiA will also produce 12 internal newsletters, one every 3 months. The production of these newsletters will be coordinated by EBN, with the input of all partners. The newsletter will function as a tool of informing all partners of milestones, key achievements, and developments in the European and African innovation ecosystems.

All newsletters will be administered and distributed through the Send in Blue platform, using European servers to the concerned stakeholders.

Through Send in Blue, the EiA will also monitor key data related to e-newsletter such as total subscriptions, recipients, open rates, click totals and rates. Other information, such as *click mapping* of specific campaigns should also inform adjustments to be made for future campaigns. Further adjustments can also be made through the duration of the project based on specific A/B testing.

News releases

12 news releases (M2-M36) will be developed by EiA during the project lifetime, with these scheduled to be released every three months to inform the press and relevant institutions of the project's developments and milestones, thus ensuring the project's visibility. These press releases will be distributed by project partners through their own communication channels (websites, newsletters, social media).

EBN will oversee the creation and dissemination of all news releases, with input from all consortium partners. All news releases will be available on the EiA website.

4.3.5 Videos

Acknowledging the importance of disseminating the outcomes in multiple formats, EiA will produce two videos of around 3 minutes each between M3 and M36. The videos will be addressing the following:

- 1 institutional video explaining how the project works
- 1 video highlighting the benefits of cross-continental collaboration

Videos will be displayed on the project website and will be disseminated through EiA social media channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube) for added visibility, as well as shared by partners through their own channels and networks.

4.4 EiA events: online, hybrid, and physical

The mobilisation of relevant stakeholders from both continents is key for the success of the project. A series of events is planned to ensure proper outreach and engagement with EiA target audiences.

The outreach capacity of events will be monitored through **quantitative and qualitative assessment** tools. This assessment should inform the consortium of which strategies work and allow it to adjust the approaches that do not work. The quantitative analysis will allow the consortium to understand the best way to engage target audiences, while the qualitative should inform of possible content adjustments.

Quantitatively, partners will be asked to use link management tools (e.g., Bitly) for the landing page url to the event page. For public events, partners will be asked to share the number of registrations per event, the turn-out rate and if possible, the retention rate. Registration forms for events should request at least: first name, last name, company, function, email, country, authorisation to keep them informed of EiA activity. All in accordance with GDPR requirements.

Qualitatively, EiA events should set out to collect feedback and suggest improvements, as well as to investigate follow-up opportunities at African and European level, either via online survey tools (e.g., Google Survey) or via email.

Zoom Meetings and Zoom Webinars are the **preferred tool for online only sessions** - except when an event requires a specific tool that the zoom platform does not provide (i.e., specific events may have a networking component among delegates that require another type of tool). The use of the same platform is justified by the desire for uniform data collection as well as by the easy-to-set YouTube and Facebook livestream capacities of Zoom.

When the event is public, partners should set up additional livestreams from Zoom to YouTube and Facebook, simultaneously. Chats on both YouTube and Facebook should also be monitored for questions asked live to speakers.

The simultaneous broadcasting on the 3 platforms serves the purpose of: giving delegates easy-to-access alternatives in case of technical issues in joining the platform or in case of the event being sold out, animating social platforms of the project, being able to acquire passers-by, being able to share a live stream video on other EiA social media.

4.4.1 EiA Webinars and E-Pitches

Online-only events are a cost-effective and interactive way to reach out to the widest possible audience in both continents. EiA will develop 3 different webinars dedicated to showcasing the Centre's portfolio services and success stories. These webinars will be delivered by BOND.

EiA will also deliver 4 E-pitching sessions. These will serve to promote innovative start-ups allowing them to pitch, for one hour, their projects and capital needs to an audience of investors. This will enable the best SMEs of the e-community to present directly in front of investor stakeholders. Given the number of projects in Europe, the focus could be on African companies to facilitate their access to investors from both continents. The E-Pitching sessions will be delivered by BPI.

4.4.2 Annual Congress & Champions Gathering

In each year of the project, EiA will organise its Annual Congress. The Congress is to be held, alternatively, in Africa and in Europe. Its aim is three-fold.

First, the Congress will gather and connect multiple stakeholders from the entrepreneurial ecosystems in Africa and Europe. It is a forum for exchanging experiences within the entrepreneurial sector, and debate common challenges, opportunities, and trends. Its goal is to expose capacity building opportunities for entrepreneurship support organisations, foster policy discussions, and recognise entrepreneurial best practices. It will welcome various communities' representatives to support EiA on shaping the best strategies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. The Congress will also offer the opportunity to hold private meetings between EiA partners, in which they will discuss the strategy and governance of the network.

Second, in the frame of each Annual Congress, EiA will host Champion's Gatherings to foster mutual learning and collaboration among the Champions of the network spread across different entrepreneurial ecosystems in Africa and Europe. The gatherings will be developed as the main space for the capacity building of Champions, following an in-depth learning journey on how to best support the entrepreneurs. It will also be an important moment for the onboarding of new champions. The Gathering will be itinerant, meaning it will be hosted by a different champion every year to allow for proper diversity and representation.

EBN (with supporting partners) is responsible for organising the Annual Congress and Champion's Gatherings. Given the international nature of this event and the geographical variety of its target audience, the events which strive to be both virtual and live (hybrid events) for higher levels of dissemination and outreach.

4.4.3 Other EiA workshops & External events

On top of the above-mentioned events, partners will run other events which are formally linked to other work packages, but also concern engagement and mutual learning practices expressed in this Communication & Dissemination Strategy.

Table 6: Other EiA workshops and external events

At the end of the entrepreneurial support programmes development process, the most successful and promising start-ups identified during the programme will have the opportunity to showcase their businesses at AfricArena, a yearly event organised by project partner MET. In total, 10 innovators will be supported through the entrepreneurial support programme - **WP2 Task 2.3**

A total of 2 Learning Expeditions (LE) will be delivered during the project implementation (one in year two and one in year three). Each LE is expected to have around 15 to 20 entrepreneur participants. As the LE is designed to familiarise the participants with local markets, they will be actively motivated to foster networking and business opportunities in accessing the local market. Ideally, the LEs will be planned back-to-back with an existing trade show or fair, such as AfricArena, to create more interest for the audience - **WP2 Task 2.4**

A selected group of EiA Champions will be invited to participate in an intensive Bootcamp training. This will include in-person training, individual coaching, guided access to methodologies and tools, and post-Bootcamp check-ins to share progress and learning - **WP3 task 3.1**

EiA will organise 2 exploitation workshops for the consortium partners to define their foreground and background and prepare the exploitation strategies for their project results - **WP 5 Task 5.1**

4.5 EiA communication campaigns

The presented tools and activities (online and off-line ones) will feed four different communication campaigns designed to:

- Each targets three specific audiences: 'BSO's (with a specific focus on incubators and accelerators), 'policy makers and social actors', and 'social entrepreneurs/under-represented group (URG)', and the full ecosystem (our facilitators).
- Ensure timely and focussed communication, dissemination, and mobilisation around the different milestones and deliverables during the implementation phases of EiA project.

Each campaign will be designed and run according to the following elements:

- a) Definition of specific objectives
- b) Identification of main target audience(s)
- c) Definition of key messages
- d) Design/use of dedicated support materials (visuals, videos, pictures, links)
- e) Preparation and implementation of an editorial plan for project website and social media

For example, in this initial phase of EiA project partners have defined the following campaign (considering that many communication tools are still under development).

Table 7: EiA communication campaign #1 – Building project awareness

**The KPIs for each campaign will be decided throughout the lifetime of the project, to allow for flexibility in adjusting the KPIs to the project needs. It is expected that each campaign will be building on the success & learnings of the previous campaign.*

Specific objectives	Create awareness of the brand-new EiA project and promote involved partners
Timeline	Feb – May 2021 & Sep – Dec 2021 (indicative: May – Aug 2022)
Main target audience(s)	<u>Project level</u> : Incubators and accelerators (I&As) - EiA champions in EU (1.A) and in

	<p>Africa (1.B)</p> <p>Facilitators - e.g., policy makers, academics, corporates, investors in the EU (2.A) and in Africa (2.B)</p> <p>Entrepreneurs, SMEs, and start-ups in the EU (3.A) and in Africa (3.B)</p> <p>Media/ multipliers and European society (focus on similar (EU) initiatives and existing platforms)</p>
Key messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EiA is a H2020 funded project strengthening the capacity of I&As and connecting innovation ecosystems in Europe and Africa. • EiA will develop capacity-building tools for incubators and accelerators to provide the best possible services to their startups and SMEs • EiA builds on the collective knowledge and experience of the ENRICH Centres, existing EU initiatives and its local I&As partners, the so-called EiA Champions • EiA is on Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn, join us and be active part of our community.
Support materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media covers and images • Project launch news release • Links to relevant articles/posts/partner initiatives
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021 EBN Congress (indicative: late September/early October) • Further events foreseen by Champions.
Editorial plan	<p><u>Mid-Mar 2021</u> > activate Twitter Weekly posts (organic posts > original content by EiA) + retweets</p> <p><u>Mid-Mar 2021</u> > Activate LinkedIn account Weekly posts (organic posts > original content by EiA) Coordinated and implemented by S2I and EBN.</p>

Table 8: EiA communication campaign #2 – Our Services

Specific objectives	<p>Create awareness around the capacity-building activities (EiA Centre’s service portfolio), mobilise partner networks’ members (EiA Champions) and community building</p>
Timeline & KPIs	<p>Nov 21 – Jan 22 & Mar 2022 – Jun 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Champions to register on EuroQuity platform (x20) • All Champions to attend Boot Camp trainings (x20 minimum) • 20 Champions’ representatives at Annual Congress • 6 news items published on partners’ networks
Main target audience(s)	<p><u>Centre level:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incubators and accelerators (I&As) - EiA champions in EU (1.A) and in Africa (1.B) • Entrepreneurs, SMEs, and start-ups in the EU (3.A) and in Africa (3.B) • Facilitators - e.g., corporates, investors in the EU (2.A) and in Africa (2.B) • Media/ multipliers and European society

Key messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EiA is a H2020 funded project strengthening the capacity of I&As and connecting innovation ecosystems in Europe and Africa • Learn more about EiA at our events (external & partner’s networks) • Learn more about and connect with the EiA Champions in Africa and Europe at the EiA Centre website • Connect with your innovation ecosystem partners on the EuroQuity platform • EiA offers develop capacity-building tools for incubators and soft-landing services for entrepreneurs to support the growth of EU-African startups and SMEs • EiA is on Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn, join us and be an active part of our community.
Support materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media covers and images • EiA Centre website and Community portal launch • EiA Centre brand identity news release • EuroQuity platform launch • EiA Annual Congress, Bootcamps, and webinars • Links to relevant articles/posts/partner initiatives
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2022 EBN Congress (indicative: late September/early October) - Further events foreseen by Champions.
Editorial plan	<p><u>Mid-Oct 2021</u> > Social Media content creation Weekly posts (organic posts > original content by EiA) + retweets Coordinated and implemented by S2I and EBN.</p> <p><u>Mid-Jan 2022</u> > Start video creation and activate YouTube Channel Video posts (content available from partners’ > original content by EiA) Coordinated by Impact Hub & S2I.</p>

As the communication campaigns run at various points during the project life cycle, content, KPIs and communication approach is updated based on learnings and on the current context of the project phase.

- Communication campaign #3: EiA Centre level: brand building and positioning EiA Centre in the innovation ecosystem (business development)
- Communication campaign #4: EiA solution and outcomes (business development & exploitation)

The full campaign design for communication campaigns #3 and #4 will be delivered in the intermediate CDM Strategy (M15).

4.6 EiA communication toolkit

All the above-mentioned communication activities and tools will be further developed, improved, and customised throughout the project’s lifetime.

To support the consortium partners in implementing all EiA communications activities, a dedicated Communication Toolkit has been created to:

1. Provide easy access to EiA printable materials, visuals, and videos
2. Collect new additional materials developed by project partners to promote EiA project and its activities in different languages
3. Organise guidelines, templates, and suggested content for the different activities/channels (events, communication campaigns, etc.)
4. Maintain a centralised database of conferences, events, and stakeholders that are of interest to EiA, which partners can easily update
5. Collect and store evidence of partners' dissemination activities and biannual dissemination reports (every 6 months)

The EiA Communication Toolkit is available in the EiA Communication and Dissemination [Google Drive](#) folder. We would like to underline that the Google Drive folder will be moved to Microsoft Teams as soon as the Internal Management folders are created, which will be made available for all consortium partners by S2i

4.7 Synergies with other projects and initiatives

Communication and relationship building with other networks and initiatives that operate in common areas of interest will be established from the early stages of the project implementation to foster potential synergies. Actively seeking collaboration opportunities with already established networks and initiatives will enable numerous “win - win” opportunities and from a communication perspective will maximise the impact of our activities in an efficient way, by leveraging multiplier and network effects. As such, actions under this channel aim to create knowledge and awareness and to explore potential common activities and ways for cooperation.

Collaborations with respect to joint dissemination activities (especially with other relevant EU funded projects) will be sought. These will take the following forms:

- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites
- Mutual support through social media accounts
- Exchange of news, invitations to external events, press releases and further dissemination actions through social media communication channels
- Invitations to participate in EiA's events.

A continuous communication pathway and synergies with complementary networks and initiatives will be sought. The exact nature of the collaboration will vary and will be decided on an ad-hoc basis, based on discussions with the representatives of the respective projects.

The below table presents relevant networks and initiatives that will be approached during the first phase of the EiA implementation:

Table 9: Relevant networks and initiatives

Name of other initiatives / networks	Description
ENRICH Centres	ENRICH is a global network of centres and hubs that

	<p>promotes the internationalisation of European science, technology, and innovation. Promoted by the European Commission through Horizon 2002, the ENRICH network currently offers services to connect European research, technology, and business organisations with three global frontrunner innovation markets: Brazil, China and the US.</p>
African European Digital Innovation Bridge (AEDIB)	<p>AEDIB has the objective to strengthen a common African European digital innovation ecosystem and promote intercontinental dialogue between African and European innovators and policymakers, AEDIB will create important opportunities for employment and pave the way for economic growth and recovery.</p>
AfriLabs	<p>Afri Labs is a network organisation of 240 innovation centres across 48 African countries. Afri Labs seeks to support hubs to raise successful entrepreneurs that will foster jobs creation and develop innovative solutions to African problems.</p>
Boost Africa Initiative	<p>A unique partnership in support of innovation and entrepreneurship across Africa has been recently launched by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the African Development Bank (AFDB) in partnership with the EC</p>
Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership	<p>The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership (AEIP) connects high-quality tech hubs from both continents to explore opportunities for mutually beneficial partnerships resulting in collaboration, exchange, and growth.</p>
AU-EU Digital 4 Development Hub	<p>The EU launched the Digital for Development (D4D) Hub, inaugurating a new era for global digital cooperation. EU Member States such as Germany, France, Belgium, Estonia, and Luxembourg are at the forefront of promoting new international partnerships on digital transformation as Team Europe.</p>
Enterprise Europe Network (EEN)	<p>The Enterprise Europe Network helps businesses innovate and grow on an international scale. It is the world's largest support network for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with international ambitions.</p> <p>The Network is active in more than 60 countries worldwide. It brings together 3,000 experts from more than 600 member organisations – all renowned for their excellence in business support.</p>
European Cluster Collaboration Platform (ECCP)	<p>The European online hub for cluster stakeholders (cluster organisations, policymakers, and other related stakeholders from the cluster ecosystem) and the reference one-stop-shop for stakeholders in third countries aiming to set up partnerships with European counterparts.</p>

5 EIA communication and dissemination targets, partners' roles, monitoring, and reporting

5.1 EIA Communication and dissemination KPIs

This section of the DCOP proposal presents the operational framework outlining EIA communication and dissemination performance indicators and targets, partners role and the monitoring and reporting procedures that will be undertaken to ensure we keep track of the activities performed on behalf of the EIA project.

The main communication activities to be implemented during the project are described in the following table. All the activities and rolls will be closely monitored and updated with the aim to better serve the EIA objectives.

Table 10: EIA performance indicators

Communication activity	Target audience	Activity description	Outreach / KPIs	Partner responsible
EiA project page	All stakeholders	Main entry point to the project, repository of news and public content. The EiA project website will act as a hub for a variety of information - based documents (reports, newsletters, press releases etc) developed under the project but also to inform relevant stakeholders regarding upcoming events and activities.	30,000 page visits	EBN & Methys
Project branding (logo, visuals, templates)	All stakeholders	A common visual entity will be created, composed of a logo, a set of templates and commonly used documents where same fonts, colours and designs will be included. All dissemination material to be developed and used within the project lifecycle will be based on the project branding.	Consistent and strict use of the EiA visual identity guidelines and templates by all partners	SPI & EBN
Promotional materials	Industry stakeholders	A set of digital and print promotional materials (i.e., brochures and flyers) will be developed to present the project and its outcome. Due to the scope of EiA Centre, the content of the different physical materials will be adapted and will consider the various specificities of the different regions for outreach. The content will be written in English; but essential information on specific activities could be presented in another language (i.e., French) to reach the targeted segments groups.	2 roll - ups, 1 brochure, 3 flyers	SPI & EBN
Social media	All stakeholders	Social media platforms will be used within the project lifecycle and will act as a complementary tool to the EiA website. EiA presence on social media channels is essential to reach a wider audience. social media will be utilised as dissemination channels. Thus, accounts will be set -up on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and LinkedIn and project activities will also be broadcasted via these channels. Well defined hashtags will be used	Social media with at 300 followers / contact on each platform	S2I & EBN

		to better manage and monitor the spread of content across all social media channels.		
E-newsletters	All stakeholders	An E- newsletter will be created every 3 months in order to provide the EiA community with information about the progress of the project. The E-newsletter will be managed using Mail Chimp and will be delivered to a wide list of stakeholders involved in the European and African innovation ecosystem. Additionally, a pdf version of the newsletter will be accessible for download via the EiA website.	12 newsletters	SPI
Videos	All stakeholders	Videos will be produced with the aim to present the EiA Centre and its activity portfolio, one institutional video and one focused on cross-continental collaboration.	2 videos produced during the project.	IMPH
Press releases	Media + freelance journalists	Press releases provide project related news to the media every 3 months	12 press releases over the course of the project	EBN

The following table puts forward examples of foreseen D&C activities along with the timing for each action and the corresponding KPIs to be used for evaluation. In addition to these activities, a range of outreach activities will be carried out to specifically reach customers for the EiA Centre (e.g., external promotional events, online outreach activities). While these activities are clearly focused on business development, they also represent a significant opportunity for the dissemination of the project and its results to stakeholders beyond customers too.

Table 11: EiA dissemination activities and Key Performance Indicators during project duration

Type	Dissemination activities	Goals / Description	KPIs
Knowledge & results transfer	EiA webinars	The consortium will develop different webinars dedicated to showcasing the Centre's portfolio services and success stories. These webinars will be tailored to different audiences.	3 webinars
	E-pitches	E-pitches promote the meeting of innovative start-ups. They will pitch, for one hour, their projects and capital needs to an audience of investors. This will enable the best SMEs of the e-community to present directly in front of Venture – capitalists, Corporate Venture – Capitalists, Business Angels, among others.	4 E-pitches

	Publications	Articles in relevant business magazines, blogs, and platforms to share the results from EiA.	At least 5 articles
	EiA Data Hub	The EiA Data Hub will act as a repository for reports and data generated by the project and the EiA Champions.	
Community Building	EiA events	<u>Annual Congress</u> : events that will bring together multiple stakeholders from the entrepreneurial ecosystem alternatively in Africa and Europe. It will be an opportunity to exchange experiences, debate challenges, opportunities, and trends. -	3 Annual Congress', 100 participants each
		<u>Champion's gatherings</u> : to foster mutual learning and collaboration among the champions of the network spread across different entrepreneurial ecosystems in Africa & Europe.	3 gatherings linked to the Annual gatherings, attended by the 20 Champion organisations.
	Clustering activities with other networks & initiatives	Clustering activities with other initiatives such as other ENRICH projects or the Africa – Europe Innovation Partnership to exchange knowledge and identify joint activities.	Attendance of at least 3 clustering events.

5.2 Partners' role

To achieve the objectives set out in the communication, dissemination and outreach plan, all consortium partners play a vital role in EiA's communication activities. Indeed, partners' activities, results, and milestones either involve communication activities or turn themselves into communication assets. In addition, partners are enhancing the online presence of EiA by providing content for the website and the project's social media channels. This important contribution can vary from a Twitter post to an event's briefing and support EiA to create a constant flow of content related to its activities.

Also, it is important to note that partners are invited to contribute (to the extent possible) to the exposure of the project through their participation in relevant events / conferences, or online sources of information (websites, newspaper, and magazines, etc) and other activities similar in nature.

At the end of each project semester, all partners will be asked to present the main dissemination actions they have carried out during the semester in question, by filling in the EiA_DR reporting template. For further information regarding the EiA communication and dissemination reporting procedures, please see section below.

Table 12: D&C Activities Breakdown per Partner

Beneficiary	Person Months	Activities
EBN	14	WP Leader ; leading T6.1 & T6.2 & T6.5; T6.6; Contributor T6.7
S2I	3	Leader T6.3; contributor T6.6 & T6.7
IMPH	3.5	Contributor T6.1 & T6.2 & T6.3 & T6.4
SPI	5.5	Leader T 6.4; contributor T6.3
AGO	1	Contributor T 6.3
BOND	1	Contributor T6.3; T6.6
CCHN	2.5	Contributor T6.3; T6.6
IHUB	1	Contributor T6.3; T6.6
MET	3.5	Contributor T 6.2; T6.3; T6.5; T6.6
SBCA	1	Contributor T6.3; T6.6
STI	1	Contributor T6.3; T6.6
BPI	2.5	Contributor T6.3; T6.6

5.3 Dissemination and Communication monitoring and reporting procedures.

Dissemination and communication reporting is essential to ensure that we keep track of all the activities that were carried out. During each project semester of the 3 - years of EiA project, a series of activities and events for disseminating EiA and its results will be carried out. To monitor the ongoing communication and dissemination flow and related outputs and outcomes, all partners are expected to fill in the internal reporting templates in a detailed manner every 6 months, so to allow WP6 leader, EBN to keep track of the progress made by the consortium against the objectives and targets set in the above-mentioned communication and dissemination strategy.

Table 13: Dissemination Reporting Procedures – reporting periods

# reporting	M	Reporting Period
1st reporting	M6	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/01/2021 to 30/06/2021
2nd reporting	M12	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/07/2021 to 31/12/2021
3rd reporting	M18	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/01/2022 to 30/06/2022
4th reporting	M24	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/07/2022 to 31/12/2022
5th reporting	M30	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/01/2023 to 30/06/2023
6th reporting	M36	Report and provide evidence(s) of activities covering the period 01/07/2023 to 31/12/2023

EBN will collect inputs and merge them in one single document to check progress against the KPIs and targets outlined above.

An excel form (EiA_DR_template) has been designed following the activities report format of Horizon 2020. Partners need to clearly specify all undertaken and accomplished activities of each reporting period and send it to EBN 3 weeks after the end of each reporting period (as highlighted in the table above). Each partner should fill in the information required and provide the appropriate evidence for each activity.

The template provided does not require too much detail, therefore, partners will be asked to be as precise as possible when reporting about the number and type of target audience reached out with specific dissemination actions. Below, some reporting guidelines to ensure consistency among the data provided by each project partner.

Table 14: EiA Internal Dissemination Reporting guidelines

- | |
|--|
| 1. When reporting about a post on a partner organisation’s website about EiA> report the |
|--|

specific number of views about that post.
2. When reporting about social media posts > report the number of impressions received by each relevant post.
3. When reporting about newsletter items > report either the number of opens (of that issue) or the number of clicks received by the relevant link in the newsletter
4. When reporting about events and webinars > report number of participants. Whether possible please specify to which STKs group they belong to.
5. When reporting about distributed brochures and flyers > report the number of printed copies and then of how many copies were distributed. For PDF version shared online > report number how many people received it or number of downloads.

5.4 Risk management

Table 15: EIA risk management

Risk number	Description of risk	Proposed risk – mitigation measures
1	Decentralised approach of EIA Centre may mean people feel disconnected from EIA brand and services	Strong network development activities network management and animation to ensure retention of customers.
2	SME requirements for access to other territories outside of those provided by EIA	Foster good working relationships with partner projects to provide an extended network.
3	Volume of interest and engagement is lower than expected	Strong strategic communication with potential to expand reach through partner & associate partner networks.
4	Lack of participants in learning expeditions	Strong and active communication campaign to ensure good visibility of services.
5	Language and cultural barriers	The materials for communication will be provided in two languages. Local champions of EIA Centre can support with cultural issues.
6	COVID – 19 pandemic travel restrictions	Shift from physical to virtual activities (if possible).

6. EIA Communication and dissemination implementation timeline

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M43	M35	M36				
Internal report						■						■						■						■															■	
Report on comms & diss activities															■																									
Outreach & membership activity report												■												■																
Communication campaign #1		■	■	■	■				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Communication campaign #2												■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Communication campaign #3																							■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Communication campaign #4																																								
Social networks			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	
Project page	■	■	■																																					
EIA Centre website	■	■	■																																					
Africa Innovation Insights		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		
Internal e-newsletter			■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■	
News releases			■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■	
Videos			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Events																																								
EIA webinar											■												■															■		
EIA e-pitches						■													■																					
EIA Annual Congress											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EIA Champions Gathering											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Branding kits			■	■	■																																			
Project brochure			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Project flyers			■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

7. Conclusion

A well designed and implemented D&C strategy is essential for raising awareness regarding the project’s concept and for exploiting its outcomes. This document aims to outline all planned D&C actions during ENRICH in Africa’s project lifetime, with a view to ensure the maximum visibility of the project, through a mix of communication channels and actions to engage with the identified stakeholder groups. The D&C strategy will also further support the EiA project by guiding our interconnected approach regarding the content we aim to publish via our channels (i.e., website, social media platforms, e-newsletters etc). Nonetheless, given the bottom - up, open nature of the project and its activities, the dissemination and communication plan will be continuously updated in line with the progress of the project.

An updated version of this DCOP will be delivered in M15 and will be based on the experience gathered during the first 15 months of the project. This will adjust the dissemination approach, where required, to increase and improve EiA outreach to the targeted stakeholders and better convey the project’s vision to the EiA community.

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